

Fraud Detection and Insurance Claim Analysis

Anjima C P
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam
Kerala
anjimacp2023a@mca.ajce.in

Ms. Shelly Shiju George
Asst.Professor Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam,
Kerala
shellyshijugeorge@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Almost a few years ago, fraud instances involving various kinds of claims have been reported by insurance companies operating as businesses. The amount fraudulently claimed is incredibly large and could result in serious issues, so in addition to the government, other organisations are attempting to identify and curtail such behaviour. Such frauds occurred in all fields of insurance claim with high severity, for example, insurance claim towards the auto sector is fraud that is frequently claimed and prominent kind, which may be done by false accident claim. Therefore, our goal is to create a project that analyses a set of insurance claim data to find fraud and inflated claims. The research uses machine learning algorithms to create a claim classification and labelling model. Machine learning model is constructed for fraudulent transaction validation using PySpark Python Library.

Keywords—Machine Learning Algorithm, PySpark, FraudCase detection, classifications

I. INTRODUCTION

Insurance fraud is the assertion that incorrect funds were obtained from an insurance company or other underwriter, as opposed to the intended funds. Two notable industries that have seen an increase in fraud are the motor and insurance industries. Frauds are categorized according to their type or source of supply. Client, negotiator, or internal sources can be used, with the last two being particularly crucial for the control framework's intended use of reads.

Frauds cover a wide range of unlawful actions that a person may do to get a favorable response from an underwriter. Frauds are categorized according to their nature, including application, inflation, identification, fabrication, manufactured, and evoked accidents, among others. This may include faking an incident, misrepresenting facts or important participants, and as a result, the cause of the injury's eventual severity. The most likely scenarios include preparing for a situation that isn't covered by insurance. presenting a situation's context incorrectly. This could involve assigning blame for accidents where the insured group is at fault or for not requiring approved security measures.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Metric capacity unit is a common abbreviation for machine learning. Computers that can learn implicitly without being explicitly programmed are included in the research of machine learning. This competency unit focuses on the extension of computer programs that have the ability to change but were previously exposed to new information. Metric capacity unit algorithms are often divided into three categories: reinforcement learning, unsupervised learning, and supervised learning. In recent years, the field of machine learning has made significant advancements in data processing. Data analysis is the main goal of data mining. Additionally, data processing makes an effort to look for plausible patterns within it.. Machine learning, on the other hand, uses knowledge to find patterns in data and improvise program actions as a result. This is a different method of obtaining knowledge for comprehending the world. The goal of determining meaning from label on the data used for instruction is mostly within the scope of supervised machine learning. Similar to supervised learning, each instance is often a base that includes an input object that is referred to as the vector and an output that includes a value that serves as an indicator to execute the model.

III. MOTIVATION

Businesses should ideally have the answers to stop fraud from happening or, if that's not possible, to catch it early enough in the strategy to do significant damage. Fraud is generally fully recognised once it occurs in businesses. Then, precautions are taken to prevent it from happening again. They are unable to resist at different points in the given time, but fraud detection is the best thing for getting rid of it from the environment and keeping it from happening again.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The following is the proposed method of the model development:

- Different models are tested on the dataset once it is obtained and cleaned.
- On the basis of the initial model performance, different features of the model are engineered and tested again.
- Once all the options area unit designed, the model is made and run victimisation completely

different values and victimisation different iteration procedures.

- A predictive model is created that predicts if an insurance claim is fraudulent or not.
- Binary Classification task takes place which gives answer between YES or NO.

V. BUILD MODEL

To implement the Logistic Regression using Python, we set the following steps:

- **Data Pre-processing step:** In this step, the data is ready in order that are often employed in code with efficiency.
 - Extraction of the dependent and freelance variables from the given dataset. Then the dataset is split as coaching and checking victimisation train test split module from sklearn library. Feature scaling is completed therefore on get correct results of predictions
- **Fitting Logistic Regression to the Training set:** LogisticRegression category of the sklearn library is employed. Classifier object is made and accustomed
 - work the model to the supply regression Predicting the test result: The model is well trained on the training set, the result is predicted by using test set data.
- **Test accuracy of the result:** Confusion matrix is employed to judge the check accuracy. In this model of fraud detection, the prediction is completed therefore on
 - check if deceitful dealings is claimed as deceitful and the other way around.
- **Visualizing the test set result:** Adjust the model fitting parameters, and repeat tests. Adjust the model fitting parameters, and repeat tests. Adjust the options or
- machine learning algorithmic program and repeat tests.

The Methodology of this project is illustrated in below figure:

Fig 1. Prediction Model

Different measures can be used to evaluate and analyse the Model Performance.

Some of the measures used in this project are:

TABLE 1. PRECISION ANALYSIS

Model	Recall	Precision	F1 Score
Logistic Regression	79	90	83
XGB	74	89	81
Decision Tree	66	79	71.86
KNN	65	75	68
Forest Tree	45	77	56

In this investigation, a number of characteristics that make it easier to distinguish between fraudulent and non-fraudulent transactions and aid in predicting the occurrence of fraud in specific transactions were identified. The machine learning models performed at varying performance levels when completely different input datasets were employed. Model rankings are derived by taking into account the average F1 score. The model performs better the higher the F1 score. According to the investigation, the formulas for Adjusted Random Forest and Changed Random Below Sampling provide the best performance models.

It cannot be assumed, however, that the order of prophetic quality will be duplicated and may vary for other datasets. Once it has been established that the feature-based models perform well within the dataset samples, it is complete.

VI. CONCLUSION

The machine learning models that were discussed and used on these datasets were able to identify the majority of false positive cases with a low false positive rate, indicating with low exactness. Some knowledge sets had serious problems with data quality, which led to relatively low levels of prediction. It would not be advisable to specify ideal algorithmic strategies or apply feature engineering processes for much greater performance given the intrinsic characteristics of different datasets. Following that, the models would be applied to particular business contexts and user priorities. This enables loss management departments to focus on different fraud scenarios and ensures that models are evolving to detect them.

V. REFERENCE

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